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BIFURCATIONS AND CHAOS IN TWO MASSES CONNECTED BY A SPRING OF VARIABLE STIFFNESS AND DAMPING COEFFICIENTS

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ABSTRACT

The bifurcation and chaotic behaviour of two forced masses that are connected by a spring of a variable stiffness and damper is considered, the masses are also connected to fixed ends on their other sides to other springs of varying stiffness and damping's i.e. the masses experience both positive and negative stiffness and damping's, here the effect of the connecting spring stiffness and the damper is considered. Local bifurcations were obtained numerically, the top Lyapunov exponents were calculated for different coupling connections. The results show that for all the cases of the connecting spring stiffness and damping's from the case where the two masses not connected at all, to the case where the connection is strong periodic and chaotic oscillations are seen in the two masses. In addition, various types of bifurcations structures are also seen.

Keyword: Bifurcation, Chaotic behaviour, Variable stiffness, Damping

INTRODUCTION

The dynamical behaviour of coupled oscillators is more complicated than that of a simple sinusoidal driven system in one degree of freedom. The nonlinear dynamics of coupled oscillators are of great importance since coupled systems are predominant in nature and many physical systems can be modelled as such. The modelled equations involve nonlinear differential equations whose solutions are sometimes impossible to obtain analytically, the coming up of high speed computers open a new window the dynamical behaviour of such systems. Coupled oscillators [1-20] are fundamental in nature due the fact that it provides the basics to the modelling of various systems consisting of physical, chemical and biological systems. Work has been done on coupled van der Pol oscillators [1-8], coupled Duffing oscillators [1, 6, and 11, 17-20] and coupled oscillators for the potential of the Ratchet type has been studied in [21-26]. To have a more general clearer picture of coupled system a very general case of a system of two degrees of freedom with external forcing functions connected to various springs and various dampers are studied here.

System Under Consideration

The system considered here is given in figure 1.0. a system of two degrees of freedom masses m_1 and m_2 are connected by a varying string of stiffness k_3 and a variable damping coefficient a_3 . The mass m_1 is excited by an external forcing $f_1(t)$ and moving on plane with friction connected to another spring and damper of stiffness and coefficients k_1, k_2 and c_1, c_2 respectively. while the second mass m_2 is also excited with a force $f_2(t)$ on a plane of negligible friction connected to another spring and damper of stiffness and coefficients k_4, k_5 and c_4, c_5 respectively [27].

Figure 1: Externally driven system of two degrees of freedom consisting of two masses coupled with a spring of variable stiffness k_3 and a damper c_3

The governing equations of motion are given by

$$\begin{aligned} m_1 \ddot{x}_1 + (c_3 - c_1) \dot{x}_1 - c_3 \dot{x}_2 + c_2 x_1^2 \dot{x}_1 + (k_1 + k_2) x_1 - k_3 x_2 + k_2 x_1^3 + \mu m_1 g \operatorname{sgn}(\dot{x}_1) &= q_1 \cos(\omega_1 t + \phi) \\ m_2 \ddot{x}_2 + (c_3 - c_4) \dot{x}_2 - c_3 \dot{x}_1 + c_5 x_2^2 \dot{x}_2 + (k_3 + k_4) x_2 - k_3 x_1 + k_5 x_2^3 &= q_2 \cos(\omega_2 t) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Where m_1 and m_2 are masses of the oscillators, $c_1 - c_5$ and $k_1 - k_5$ are the damping and stiffness coefficients, with q_1 and q_2 are amplitudes of the exciting forces with corresponding frequencies ω_1 and ω_2 and ϕ denotes a phase shift between the exiting forces.

In nondimensional form the equations reduce to

$$\begin{aligned} y_1'' + (\alpha_3 - \alpha_1) y_1' - \alpha_3 (KM^{-1})^{0.5} y_2' + \gamma_1 y_1^2 y_1' + (\kappa_1 + \kappa_3) y_1 - \kappa_3 (KM^{-1})^{0.5} y_2 + y_1^3 + R \operatorname{sgn}(y_1') &= B_1 \cos(\tau + \phi) \\ y_2'' + M(\alpha_3 - \alpha_4) y_2' - M \alpha_3 (KM^{-1})^{0.5} y_1' + \gamma_2 K y_2^2 y_1' + M(\kappa_3 + \kappa_4) y_2 - M \kappa_3 (KM^{-1})^{0.5} y_1 + y_2^3 &= M^{1.5} K^{-0.5} B_2 \cos(\nu \tau) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Where

$$\begin{aligned} \tau = \omega_1 t, y_1 = (\omega_1 m_1^{0.5})^{-1} k_2^{0.5} x_1, y_2 = (\omega_1 m_1^{0.5})^{-1} k_5^{0.5} x_2, M = m_1 m_2^{-1}, K = k_2 k_5^{-1}, \nu = \omega_2 \omega_1^{-1} \\ B_1 = q_1 \omega_1^{-3} m_1^{1.5} k_5^{0.5}, B_2 = q_2 \omega_1^{-3} m_1^{1.5} k_5^{0.5}, \alpha_1 = C_1 (m_1 \omega_1)^{-1}, \alpha_3 = C_3 (m_1 \omega_1)^{-1}, \alpha_4 = C_4 (m_1 \omega_1)^{-1} \\ \kappa_1 = k_1 m_1^{-1} \omega_1^{-2}, \gamma_1 = \omega_1 C_2 k_2^{-1}, \gamma_2 = \omega_1 C_4 k_2^{-1}, \kappa_3 = k_3 m_1^{-1} \omega_1^{-2}, \kappa_4 = k_4 m_1^{-1} \omega_1^{-2}, R = \mu g \omega_1^{-3} k_2^{0.5} m_1^{-0.5} \end{aligned}$$

As a system of first order equations it is written as

$$\begin{aligned} y_1' &= z_1 \\ z_1' &= -(\kappa_1 + \kappa_3 + y_1^2) y_1 + \alpha_3 (KM^{-1})^{0.5} y_2 - (\alpha_3 - \alpha_1) y_1 + \kappa_3 (KM^{-1})^{0.5} y_2 - \gamma_1 y_1^2 z_1 - R \operatorname{sgn}(z_1) \\ &+ B_1 \cos(\varphi_1 + \varphi) \\ y_2' &= z_2 \\ z_2' &= -(M(\kappa_1 + \kappa_3) + y_2^2) y_2 - M(\alpha_3 - \alpha_4) y_2 + \kappa_3 M (KM^{-1})^{0.5} y_1 - \gamma_2 K y_2^2 z_2 + M^{1.5} K^{-1.5} B_2 \cos(\nu \varphi_1) \\ \varphi_1' &= 1 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Bifurcations and Chaos

This section aims in finding in finding the routes that lead to chaos in for the system under consideration given by (1). Bifurcation diagrams are very good for numerical as well as experimental study when there is a tunable parameter in the system. Here the forcing amplitude B_1 of the mass m_1 is considered as the variable parameter. This control parameter is varied through from 0.0 to a maximum value of 0.5 for the stiffness of the coupling spring k_3 at 0.2, 0.3, and 0.4, $k_1 = k_4 = -0.8163$ and damping $\alpha_1 = \alpha_4 = -0.2857$, $\alpha_3 = 0.0, 0.05, 0.1063$ and 0.1153 . and a forcing amplitude for m_2 at $B_2 = 0.2799$ local bifurcation structures are presented in this section. A more quantitative approach to support the above bifurcation structure for chaos is the use of the Lyapunov exponent. The Lyapunov exponent is one of the most important tools of understanding chaos, obtained by examining the sensitive dependence on initial conditions to the system. A positive Lyapunov exponent for chaos, zero exponent for quasiperiodicity and negative exponent for periodic orbits [28].

Defining new variables:
$$\begin{aligned} u_1(t) &= x_1(t), u_2(t) = \dot{x}_1(t), \\ u_3(t) &= x_2(t), u_4(t) = \dot{x}_2(t) \end{aligned}$$

The system (1) can written as

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{u}_1 &= u_2 \\ \dot{u}_2 &= -(k_1 + k_3 + u_1^2)u_1 + \alpha_3 u_4 - (\alpha_3 - \alpha_4)u_2 + k_3 u_3 + b_1 \cos(\phi) \\ \dot{u}_3 &= u_4 \\ \dot{u}_4 &= -(k_1 + k_3 + u_3^2)u_3 - (\alpha_3 - \alpha_4)u_4 + k_3 u_1 + \alpha_3 u_2 + b_1 \cos(\phi) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Whose linearized equations in variational form is given by

$$\begin{pmatrix} \delta \dot{u}_1(t) \\ \delta \dot{u}_2(t) \\ \delta \dot{u}_3(t) \\ \delta \dot{u}_4(t) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ -(k_1 + k_3 + 3x^2) & -(\alpha_3 - \alpha_4) & k_3 & \alpha_3 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ k_3 & \alpha_3 & -(k_1 + k_3 + 3z^2) & -(\alpha_3 - \alpha_4) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \delta u_1(t) \\ \delta u_2(t) \\ \delta u_3(t) \\ \delta u_4(t) \end{pmatrix} \quad (5)$$

Written in compact form as

$$\delta \dot{U}(t) = L_{ij}(U(t)) \delta U$$

Where the Lyapunov exponent is defined as

$$\lambda = \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\|\delta U(t)\|}{\|U(0)\|} \quad (6)$$

The top Lyapunov exponents of the system are computed using the definition given by (6) and the results are also presented along with the local bifurcation structures below.

Figure 2: Top: Bifurcation diagram, the x-axis is the forcing amplitude B1 in the range [0:0.5] while the y-axis is the position of the mass m1. Bottom: Is top Lyapunov exponent for forcing function of amplitude B1 in the range also of [0:0.5] on the x-axis while the y-axis is just a number called the Lyapunov exponent usually denoted by λ for damping $\alpha_3 = 0.0$ and coupling strength $k_3 = 0.0$ (No damping no coupling)

Figure 3: Top: The x-axis is the forcing amplitude B1 in the range [0:0.5]: The y-axis is the position of the mass m1. Bottom: B1 in the range also of [0:0.5] on the x-axis: The y-axis is the Lyapunov λ for damping $\alpha_3 = 0.2$ and coupling strength $k_3 = 0.2$ (small damping and coupling case)

Figure 4: Top: The x-axis is the forcing amplitude B1 in the range [0:0.5]: The y-axis is the position of the mass m1. Bottom: B1 in the range also of [0:0.5] on the x-axis: The y-axis is the Lyapunov λ for damping $\alpha_3 = 0.3$ and coupling strength $k_3 = 0.3$ (intermediate damping and coupling case)

Figure 5: Top: The x-axis is the forcing amplitude $B1$ in the range $[0:0.5]$: The y-axis is the position of the mass $m1$. Bottom: $B1$ in the range also of $[0:0.5]$ on the x-axis: The y-axis is the Lyapunov λ for damping $\alpha3 = 0.4$ and coupling strength $k3 = 0.4$ (strong damping and coupling case)

Figure 6: Top: The x-axis is the forcing amplitude $B1$ in the range $[0:0.5]$: The y-axis is the position of the mass $m1$. Bottom: $B1$ in the range also of $[0:0.5]$ on the x-axis: The y-axis is the Lyapunov λ for damping $\alpha3 = 0.2$ and coupling strength $k3 = 0.4$ (weak damping and strong coupling case)

Figure 7: Top: The x-axis is the forcing amplitude $B1$ in the range $[0:0.5]$: The y-axis is the position of the mass $m1$. Bottom: $B1$ in the range also of $[0:0.5]$ on the x-axis: The y-axis is the Lyapunov λ for damping $\alpha3 = 0.4$ and coupling strength $k3 = 0.2$ (strong damping and weak coupling case)

CONCLUSION

The work considered the system of two masses connected to fixed ends by springs of variable spring stiffness also connected dampers. The two masses are connected to each other by another spring of a varying stiffness and a damper. This coupling spring and the coupling damper was subjected to various changes to see the effect on the

dynamical behaviour of the two masses. The cases of no coupling at all, weak, intermediate and strong interactions were considered, the forcing amplitude B_1 was also used as a tunable parameter in the range of 0.0 to 0.5. The local bifurcation structures and the top Lyapunov exponents were presented in figures 2 through 7 as indicators for chaos. From these results it can be concluded that for this system the effect of the coupling stiffness and damping has no effect on stabilizing the dynamics since from the two masses not connected at all through to the case of strong coupling connection the system exhibit period and chaotic orbits and all types of bifurcation structures. The tunable parameter B_1 can be in stabilizing the system dynamics, since from the figures it can be seen that for low values of B_1 and there are other values of B_1 , like around $B_1=0.4$ stable periodic orbits are seen throughout, meaning that a proper choice of B_1 will be useful in finding non chaotic orbits.

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